

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF ECONOMETRICAL MODELING OF SERVICE NETWORKS TO THE RURAL POPULATION

Quvatova Gulzoda Faxriddin qizi

Trainee teacher of the "Economics and exact sciences" department

International innovation university

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8431472>

Abstract: This article discusses the importance of econometric modeling of service networks for rural residents, the role of rural residents in service networks, the quality of services provided in villages, and the state of rural infrastructure.

Keywords: Rural population, infrastructure, service networks, econometric modeling

The importance of econometric modeling of rural population service networks is shown in:

- material, labor and money resources are used rationally;
- serves as a leading tool in the analysis of economic and natural processes;

It will be possible to introduce some corrections during forecasting in the development of service networks for the rural population;

not only a deep analysis of service networks, but also an opportunity to discover their unexplored new laws. Also, with their help, it will be possible to predict the future development of service networks;

along with the automation of calculation work, it eases mental work, it is possible to organize and manage the work of service workers on a scientific basis.

In econometric modeling, control systems are defined as changes in the task variable with a given precision (with a fixed error) according to the law. In the design and operation of automatic control systems, it is necessary to select the parameters of S system that can ensure the required control accuracy, as well as stability in the transition process.

If the system is stable, then its behavior with time, the maximum deviation of the adjustment variable in the transient process, the time of the transient process, etc., are of practical interest. It is possible to draw conclusions about the properties of automatic control systems of different classes based on the types of differential equations that most closely describe the processes in the system. The order of the differential equation and the value of the coefficients fully determine the static and dynamic parameters of the system.

Due to the increase in the quality and variety of services provided in villages, the population's level of use of services is increasing. Taking this into account, it is planned to establish 2 "Guzar" type shopping and household complexes in each village. In practice, 4 "Guzar" were built and commissioned in the last period of this year. The services provided in the retail trade and catering systems in the republic are developing at high rates. The total traffic volume increased by 17.7% in January-April 2019 compared to the same period of the previous year, and 36% of the total traffic volume corresponds to rural areas. As a result of the increase of stationary stores from year to year, the volume of retail sales achieved through them increased by 38.4%. As of May 1 of this year, the number of stationary stores serving in rural areas is more than 20 thousand, of which 40% are food products, 32% are non-food goods, and 28% are mixed goods retail stores. . The total volume of goods sold per capita in the villages in January-April was 94,000 soums. Communication and information, financial and banking services are increasingly developing in rural areas. As of May 1, 2021, a total of 367 telephone exchanges in the republic, including 72 in 87 villages, will be repaired this year. The share of the total volume of communication, postal and information services provided in rural areas will increase by 1.6%. 32% are non-food stores and 28% are general merchandise retailers. The total volume of goods sold per capita in the villages in January-April was 94,000 soums. Communication and information, financial and banking services are increasingly developing in rural areas. As of May 1, 2021, a total of 367 telephone exchanges in the republic, including 72 in 87 villages, will be repaired this year. The share of the total volume of communication, postal and information services provided in rural areas will increase by 1.6%. 32% are non-food stores and 28% are general merchandise retailers. The total volume of goods sold per capita in the villages in January-April was 94,000 soums. Communication and information, financial and banking services are increasingly developing in rural areas. As of May 1, 2021, a total of 367 telephone exchanges in the republic, including 72 in 87 villages, will be repaired this year. The share of the total volume of communication, postal and information services provided in rural areas will increase by 1.6%. finance and banking services are increasingly developing. As of May 1, 2021, a total of 367 telephone exchanges in the republic, including 72 in 87 villages, will be repaired this year. The share of the total volume of communication, postal and information services provided in rural areas will increase by 1.6%. finance and banking services are increasingly developing. As of May 1, 2021, a total of 367 telephone exchanges in the republic, including 72

in 87 villages, will be repaired this year. The share of the total volume of communication, postal and information services provided in rural areas will increase by 1.6%.

Service networks are diverse and have distinct characteristics.

List of used literature:

1. Raximov A.N. Aholiga xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining rivojlanishini ekonometrik modellashtirish (Qashqadaryo viloyatimisolida): iqt. fan. fal. dok. diss. – T.: TDIU, 2020. –165 b.
2. Kh.S. Mukhitdinov, A.N. Rakhimov. The forecast for the development of the public services sector. Scopus, Solid State Technology, December 2020, Vol 63, № 6 (2020)
3. Abduraxmanov A.S. / Aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda xizmatlar sohasini rivojlantirish journal of marketing, business and management(jmbm)/sjif factor: 4.28, 36-37 pages.
4. Qodirov, Farrux. "Econometric modeling of medical services in the territories." International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies ICISCT. 2022.
5. Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li. Econometric modeling of the development of medical services to the population of the region / Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. 2022/5/9. 1.1 Economical sciences.
6. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "Aholiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining kelgusi holatini bashoratlash." Servis" ilmiy-amaliy jurnal (2022): 56-59.
7. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "Econometric modeling of the development of medical services to the population of the region." Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities 2.1.1 Economical sciences (2022).

8. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "Creation of electronic medical base with the help of software packages for medical services in the regions." Conferencea (2022): 128-130.
9. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "Importance of kash-health web portal in the development of medical services in the regions." Conferencea (2022): 80-83.
10. Qodirov, F. "Ijtimoiy va xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirishda sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlarini ekonometrik modellashtirishning ahamiyati". O'zR FA V.I.Romanovskiy nomidagi Matematika instituti, 2022.
11. Qodirov, F. "Qishloq aholisiga sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlari ko'rsatish tarmoqlari rivojlanish mexanizmining statistik tahlili". Andijon Mashinasozlik Instituti, 2022.
12. Qodirov, F. "Aholiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining kelgusi holatini bashoratlash". Samarqand iqtisodiy va servis instituti, 2022.
13. Qodirov, F. "Optimum solutions for the development of medical services in private clinics". Muhammad al-xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti Qarshi filiali, 2022.
14. Qodirov, F. "Qashqadaryo viloyati aholisiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlarini rivojlantirishning istiqbollari". «O'ZBEKISTON QISHLOQ VA SUV XO'JALIGI» àà «AGRO ILM», 2022.
15. Qodirov, F. "Hududlarda tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatishni ekonometrik modellashtirish". Xorazm ma'mun akademiyasi axborotnomasi, 2022.
16. Qodirov, F. "Qashqadaryo hududi aholisiga xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari va ularga ta'sir etuvchi omillar". "O'zbekiston Qishloq Va Suv xo'jaligi" Jurnali, 2022.
17. QODIROV, F. "Axoliga xizmat ko'rsatish soxasining modellashtirishni tizimli imitatsiya qilish". IJTISODIY ILMIY-AMALIY OYLIK NASHR, 2022.
18. Qodirov, F. "Hududlarda tibbiy xizmatlarni dasturiy paketlar yordamida elektron tibbiy bazasini yaratish". O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Va o'rta Maxsus ta'lim Vazirligi Namangan Muhandislik-Qurilish Instituti, 2022.
19. Farrux Qodirov. "Aholiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatishdan olingan daromad va xarajatlarni imitatsion modeli". " Moliya bozorini rivojlantirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy tendensiyalari va istiqbollari" mavzusidagi Respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi materiallar to'plami. 2022/11/5
20. F.E Qodirov, Aholiga tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatishdan olingan daromad va xarajatlarni imitatsion modeli, toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti "o'zbekiston iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishning ilmiy, 922

